

A new species of *Gynacantha* Rambur, 1842, from Papua New Guinea (Odonata: Aeshnidae)

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Abstract. *Gynacantha nuda* sp. nov. is described based on a male from Southern Highlands Province, Papua New Guinea. It is the largest known species of the genus to be reported from New Guinea. Characters of the adult male are illustrated, the affinities of the new species are discussed, and a key is presented to males of the *Gynacantha* species recorded from New Guinea.

Further key words. Dragonfly, Anisoptera, *Gynacantha nuda* sp. nov.

Introduction

Dragonflies of the aeshnid genus *Gynacantha* Rambur, 1842 are large, robust species that are active mostly at dawn and dusk. Six *Gynacantha* species have previously been recorded from the island of New Guinea. They are *Gynacantha bayadera* Selys, 1891, *G. calliope* Lieftinck, 1953, *G. heros* Theischinger & Richards, 2012, *G. kirbyi* Krüger, 1898, *G. mocsaryi* Förster, 1898, and *G. rosenbergi* Brauer, 1867. All six species are recorded and illustrated by ORR & KALKMAN (2015), five of them by MICHALSKI (2012) and four of them by MARTIN (1909).

A recent biodiversity survey in the Kikori River headwaters of southern Papua New Guinea revealed a *Gynacantha* species that is new to science and that represents the largest member of the genus known from New Guinea. It is described below as *Gynacantha nuda* sp. nov.

Material and methods

Descriptive terminology follows CHAO (1953) and WATSON & O'FARRELL (1991), except for descriptions of wing venation that follow PETERS & THEISCHINGER (2007). Coloration is given as detectable from the preserved material. Measurements are given in millimetres (mm). All illustrations were done with the aid of a camera lucida and are not to scale. The holotype of *Gynacantha nuda* sp. nov. is deposited in the collection of the South Australian Museum, Adelaide (SAM).

Gynacantha nuda sp. nov.

(Figs 1–6, 16–18, 21–22)

Material studied

Holotype ♂ (SAM 07-001430), Papua New Guinea, Southern Highlands Province, upper Kikori River basin, Camp 7 (6°26.900'S, 142°57.587'E, 365 m a.s.l.), S.J. Richards leg., 04-viii-2014.

Etymology

The specific name, a declinable adjective, (*nudus* 3, Latin for naked) refers to the male's lack of any denticles along the margin of the genital fossa.

A very large, sombre-coloured dragonfly with distinct dark spots on the sides of synthorax and with very pale mediodorso-lateral and pale postero-dorsal abdominal markings (Figs 1, 2); the male without denticles along margin of genital fossa (Figs 4, 16), moderately thin waist on S3 (Figs 3, 17) and sub-basally angulated superior anal appendages (Figs 6, 18).

Male (Holotype) (Figs 1–6, 16–18, 21–22).

Head – Labium yellowish to medium brown; labrum including labial palps and base of mandibles brownish yellow to blackish brown, tip of mandibles shining reddish to blackish brown; genae greenish grey to brown; remainder of face greenish grey; top of frons pale greenish grey with distinct narrow but wide-stemmed black T-mark; vertex black; antennae pale to dark brown; occipital triangle small, pale greenish yellow; detectable portion of postgenae medially dark, almost black, laterally pale yellow.

Thorax – Pronotum greyish yellow to pale yellowish brown. Synthoracic pleura yellowish to greyish brown, darkest along the black dorsal carina, palest along ridges and in ante-alar sinus, spotted with six small black patches each side as follows: along mesopleural suture next to mesocoxa and immediately below sub-alar ridge, along metapleural suture between metakatepisternum and metepimeron and somewhat below sub-alar ridge, narrowly around the metastigma and along ventral edge of metepimeron adjacent to anterior angle of metapostepimeron. Posterior margin of metapostepimeron, crests of ante-alar and sub-alar ridges and particularly area adjacent to posterior end of sub-alar ridge also distinctly darkened. Terga largely brownish yellow to dark greyish brown. Poststernum yellow to pale greyish brown with anteromedian angle black. Legs brown with coxae somewhat paler, trochanters somewhat darker and knees very narrowly darkened.

Wings – Membrane hyaline, suffused with dark brown basal to Ax1, with paler brown distally from level of triangle; venation not very dense, blackish brown; membranule very small, pale greyish to yellowish white. Ax1 and Ax9 strengthened in Fw, Ax1 and Ax9–10 in Hw. Antenodals 29–30/21–22; postnodals 25–26/26. Pterostigma pale brownish yellow, not braced, 3.3 mm long in fore wing, 3.0 mm long in hind wing, overlying 3–5 cells. Cuq 9–10/7–8; bq 8/7–8; no mq in either wing. Triangles with 7/7–8 cells; hypertriangles with 10–12/9 cells. IR2 fork asymmetrical and well proximal of pterostigma; field between IR2 and Rspl and field between MA and Mspl up to 6 cells deep; only a single row of cells between MP and CuA in hind wing; anal loop 3 cells wide and up to 5 cells deep; anal triangle 3-celled in both wings; at least 3 rows of paranal cells. Other details as visible on photo (Fig. 1).

Abdomen – Largely brownish black dorsally and laterally with intersegmental membranes black and with side of S1 and S2 and ventral edge of S3–8 brownish yellow to pale greyish brown; S4–8 from base backwards considerably narrowed; S2: auricles dorsally greenish grey to black, ventrally yellow, with 7 small but well defined teeth; margin of genital fossa at most finely hirsute and without denticles; S3 less than three times as long as

wide at apex, after the constriction (waist) which is approximately 1.6 mm wide, considerably expanded, attaining at apex about one half the width of S2 across the auricles; S2–8 with pair of narrow pale yellow mediodorsal patches along transverse carina connecting with pale patches along ventral edge; a pair of pale yellow oval posterodorsal spots on S3–7 and a weak indication of such spots on S8; S9 and S10 brown with black mediodorsal smudge of variable width and black posterior margin (dorsally and laterally). Sternite 1 brownish yellow with anterior margin largely black; secondary genitalia yellowish to greyish brown; sternites 3–7 greyish to brownish black; sternites 8 and 9 dull yellowish to greyish brown; bipartite sternite 11 black. Superior anal appendages 9.7 mm long, slender, black, in dorsal view with inner margin very slightly and smoothly curved, and without distinct sub-basal excavation or bulge, in lateral view with distinct sub-basal angle of approximately 155°; tips pointing almost straight backward; inferior appendage largely yellow, in dorsal view tapered, with sides convex in basal half, thence narrow, parallel sided, with apex rounded, black. Superior anal appendages appearing in dorsal view markedly more than four times as long as inferior appendage.

Measurements [mm] – Hind wing 57.0; abdomen plus appendages 66.5.

Female

Unknown.

Habitat

The only known specimen of *Gynacantha nuda* was flying at dusk in the clearing used for a field camp on the site of an old village. The surrounding forest included areas modified by subsistence farming and contained a patchwork of early and late successional rainforest vegetation. A wide diversity of aquatic habitats occurred in close proximity to the camp including a sago swamp, and numerous small muddy and a few larger clear rocky streams.

This species is currently known only from the Hegigio River drainage, a tributary of the Kikori River in Southern Highlands Province, Papua New Guinea.

Figures 1–6. *Gynacantha nuda* sp. nov., holotype male: 1 – lateral view; 2 – anal appendages, lateral; 3 – S1–3, ventral; 4 – part of S2, ventral, showing margin of genital fossa; 5, 6 – anal appendages: 5 – dorsal; 6 – lateral.

Differential diagnosis

The male of *G. nuda* sp. nov. is easily separated from all known *Gynacantha* species from New Guinea by lacking denticles along the margins of the genital fossa (Figs 4, 16, 21). The new species shares with *G. kirbyi* and *G. heros* the presence of dark spots on the side of the thorax, and superior anal appendages that are much longer than the inferior appendage and that are sub-basally and apically not particularly modified. *Gynacantha nuda* sp. nov. differs from *G. kirbyi* in its larger size, in the differences in width between different sections of abdominal segments 1, 2, and 3 (smaller than in *G. kirbyi*, Fig. 14) and in having the superior anal appendages at least four times as long as the inferior versus markedly less than four times as long in *G. kirbyi*. *Gynacantha nuda* differs furthermore from *G. heros* and *G. kirbyi* (Figs 19, 20) by the distinct angle (approximately 155°) near the base of the superior anal appendages as detectable in lateral view (Figs 6, 18, 22). The other four New Guinean species lack the dark spots on the side of the thorax and are furthermore separated from *G. nuda* sp. nov. by their smaller size (*G. bayadera* has Hw of 42 mm or less), the sub-basally excavated superior anal appendages (*G. calliope*, Fig. 8), the apically spatulate superior anal appendages (*G. moscsaryi*, Fig. 10) or have the differences in width between different sections of segments 1, 2, and 3 greater (*G. moscsaryi*, Fig. 9) or markedly smaller (*G. rosenbergi*, Fig. 11). A key to the males of New Guinean *Gynacantha* is presented below.

right page: **Figures 7–18.** *Gynacantha* species, male: 7 – *G. bayadera*, anal appendages, dorsal, modified from RIS (1915); 8 – *G. calliope*, anal appendages, dorsal, modified from LIEFTINCK (1953); 9, 10 – *G. moscsaryi*, modified from WATSON et al. (1991): 9 – S2–3, dorsal; 10 – anal appendages, dorsal; 11, 12 – *G. rosenbergi*: 11 – S2–3, dorsal, from WATSON et al. (1991); 12 – anal appendages, dorsal, modified from THEISCHINGER & HAWKING (2006); 13–15 – *G. kirbyi*: 13 – part of S2, ventral, showing the armed margin of genital fossa; 14 – S1–3, ventral, modified from THEISCHINGER & RICHARDS (2012); 15 – basal portion of anal appendages, lateral; 16–18 – *G. nuda* sp. nov.: 16 – part of S2, ventral, showing the unarmed margin of genital fossa; 17 – S1–3, ventral; 18 – basal portion of anal appendages, lateral.

Figures 19–22. *Gynacantha* species, male: 19, 20 – *G. kirbyi*: 19 – ventral portion of S2, lateral; 20 – anal appendages, lateral; 21, 22 – *G. nuda* sp. nov.: 21 – ventral portion of S2, lateral; 22 – anal appendages, lateral.

Key to the males of *Gynacantha* from New Guinea

- 1a – Small species with Hw not longer than 42 mm; anal appendages as in Fig. 7 *G. bayadera*
- 1b – Larger species with Hw longer than 44 mm 2
- 2a – Superior anal appendages with sub-basal inner excavation (Fig. 8) *G. calliope*
- 2b – Superior anal appendages without sub-basal inner excavation 3
- 3a – Very slim, slender waisted species (Fig. 9); superior anal appendages about 2½ times as long as inferior appendage and with broad spatulate apical portion (Fig. 10) *G. mocsaryi*
- 3b – Stout (Fig. 11) or slim (as in Figs 14, 17) species; superior anal appendages at least three times as long as inferior appendage and with apical section only moderately widened (as in, or similar to, Figs 5, 12) 4
- 4a – Very stout species with ‘waist’ on S3 rather wide (Fig. 11); anal appendages as in Fig. 12 *G. rosenbergi*
- 4b – Slimmer species with ‘waist’ on S3 rather narrow (as in, or similar to, Figs 14, 17); anal appendages as, or similar to Fig. 5 5
- 5a – Large species with dense venation (markedly more than 30 postnodals in both wings); superior anal appendages in lateral view sub-basally almost straight *G. heros*
- 5b – Large or smaller species with more open venation (markedly fewer than 30 postnodals in both wings); superior anal appendages in lateral view sub-basally straight (Figs 15, 20) or distinctly angulated (Figs 18, 22) 6
- 6a – Numerous denticles along margin of genital fossa (Figs 13, 19); S3 approximately four times as long as wide at apex (Fig. 14); superior anal appendages in lateral view sub-basally straight (Figs 15, 20) *G. kirbyi*
- 6b – No denticles along margin of genital fossa (Figs 16, 21); S3 approximately three times as long as wide at apex (Fig. 17); superior anal appendages in lateral view sub-basally distinctly angulated (Figs 18, 22) *G. nuda* sp. nov.

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